

VigilHate - VIGILANT CITIZENS AGAINST HATE: How to counter bystander apathy and increase citizens' commitment against online hate speech?"

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Project abstract: Hate crime rates grow steadily, although official statistics fail to express the real extent of such crimes. A cause of this gap is the fact that citizens often fail to report witnessed hate crimes. By failing to report, they blur the real magnitude of these crimes, legitimize and perpetuate their occurrence. According to the EU, civil society should be accountable in this process and cooperate with victims, namely by reporting hate crime. Hate speech is the most common hate crime and the one that most enacts a bystander effect. Hate speech is even more problematic in online contexts, in which people feel protected from face-to-face interaction. Moreover, in online contexts, social control mechanisms are perceived to be ineffective in controlling online misbehaviour. This project relies on a social responsibility enhancing approach to combat online hate speech. We will study psychosocial processes underlying bystander apathy facing online hate speech and test the effectiveness of prosocial determinants on stimulating individuals' moral self-regulation aimed at decreasing their own bystander apathy and at the increasing report of online hate speech. Results might be promising to inform social media platforms about additional strategies to combat this misbehaviour and to provide information for anti-discrimination NGOs' activists, politicians and moral entrepreneurs acting in anti-discrimination domains to decide the best strategies towards empowering "citizens against hate".

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1. Output summary (Data collection)

This project is divided into 5 studies with different types of data, collecting methods and management rules. This project is financed by the “La Caixa” Foundation and FCT; grant number (Nº SR20-00136), and responds to all existing requirements related to the RDM and Protection of Personal Data. The Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences of the University of Porto follows the Regulation of the Ethics Committee which defines a set of rules to guide projects, including this one, which must be read and applied by all project collaborators. All members of the project follow the established, updated and monitored Data Management Plan during the development of the work and after its finalization.

Collected data during this project is important in both scientific and social dimensions. This research project and data can help to reduce the bystander effect in general and promote online hate speech reports in particular, awakening citizens to contribute to legitimize and perpetuate reports of online hate speech occurrence. The literature review showed that there is little data related to this topic that can be reused, raising the value of the data that we will collect and open with others after the conclusion of the project. Moreover, these data and studies can be reusable in other research studies, not only in psychology domains but in other social sciences domains such as Sociology, Political Science, and Law.

This project will include: **RAW data** (a database with name, surname, and email for scheduling the focus group session in Study 2), answers to questionnaires, session video files); **transcripts** (session video files will be transcribed to word documents and will be destroyed after data processing); and **processed data** (excel, spss files processed from data collected through questionnaires; word files processed from transcripts) that will be published after the project conclusion and after the publishing of the papers related to the data.

Study 1. Creation and validation of a bystander effect scale for the Portuguese population

This study involves the Portuguese population of 18 years or over and aims at creating a bystander effect scale facing online hate speech behaviour. This study includes one questionnaire approved by the Ethics Committee, that will be responded to only after the signing of the informed consent, the clarification of the goals of the project, and the explanation of rights under the General Data Protection Regulation (<https://gdpr-info.eu/>). In this study, more or less 200 participants are expected (can be adjusted according to the project's needs).

The data will be collected through an online anonymous questionnaire with the Qualtrics tool for the online questionnaire. This survey will be disseminated on social networks and other digital media (more detail will be added on the next version of the DMP).

Study 2. Focus groups with immigrants and Portuguese population on online hate speech

This study involves four focus groups, namely one for female Brazilian immigrants, one for male Brazilian immigrants, one for Chinese immigrants and one for Portuguese citizens, with 18 or overage and aims to collect the opinions and perceptions, on issues

related to online hate speech against immigrants, and specifically the specificity of online hate speech against Brazilian and Chinese immigrants.

The data will be collected through Zoom group sessions by 8 to 10 participants plus a moderator and an assistant and will last up to 90 minutes. These group sessions will occur after the signing of the informed consent, explaining the goal of the study, and their rights under the General Data Protection Regulation and their participation in this type of methodology. The sessions will be recorded, transcribed and processed, with participants' agreement.

Nevertheless, for this study, some personal data are necessary for scheduling the focus group session and for monetary compensation (through an FNAC Digital Gift Card worth €10) to participants (this will be included in the informed consent). We will collect: name, surname, email, sociodemographic data such as gender, age, nationality, education, professional status and district of residence. Although we collect names and surnames, the participants must indicate their pseudonyms for participating in the session, in order to maintain their anonymity in the presence of other participants; in the registration form, we will ask for this pseudonym in order to confirm the presence of the person at the time of the session (namely when this name appears in the Zoom waiting room). The database with personal information will be processed according to their pseudonyms in order to diminish the risk for personal data exposure.

For all situations, an instruction manual will be sent to participants prior to the session, with an explanation of how the participants can change their name before the starting Zoom session and some basic rules of participation. The personal data will be accessible only by the researcher in charge of RDM: Isabel Pinto and Catarina Carvalho. After completing all the sessions and sending the vouchers, these data will be deleted.

In terms of data storage, only indicated researchers will have access to the collected data and to the session video files, which will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto. Moreover, data can also be stored on Drive U.Porto, but this will be defined in more detail, in a later version of DMP. Session video files will be destroyed as soon as the discussion group session is transcribed and verified. Informed consent forms and information from contact will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto separately from the video files and session transcripts in an encrypted archive password-protected, accessible only to the PI Isabel Pinto, Catarina Carvalho, and Susana Salgado.

Finally, the data analysis will be carried out after the anonymization of the collected data, that is, the analysis will be performed on the transcribed data participant's real name will not be associated with each intervention. In order to accomplish this goal, a unique code will be assigned to each of the participants and all identifying information (such as name and email address) will be removed. This code will be kept in an encrypted, password-protected file, accessible only to the principal investigator. In this way, any member of the team can perform this analysis without compromising the privacy of the participants.

Study 3. Assessing bystander attitudes and effect on online hate speech

Data will be collected through anonymous online questionnaires with hate speech situations, based on results of Studies 1 and 2, the scale created and validated in Study 1 and other measures, already published in the literature and considered as fundamental to assess psychosocial processes that determine bystander effect and that may be related to the stimulation of individuals' moral self-regulation to combat bystander effect. The

questionnaire will be disseminated through social networks and other available digital media (we will indicate more information on the next version of DMP). As this study depends on the results of Studies 1 and 2, we will organize this process in more detail later. In the same manner, more detailed information will be added in the next DMP version, and if necessary new authorization from the Ethics Committee will be requested. As in Studies 1 and 2, all participants will sign the informed consent form, in which the conditions for participation and participants' rights will be explained.

This study will include 2 groups: Portuguese citizens and immigrants (i.e. potential victims of online hate speech) expecting a total of 800 participants.

Study 4. Changing bystander attitudes toward online hate speech

This study will include participants in one of 6 possible experimental conditions aimed to test each of the following determinants on increasing participants' moral self-regulation: (1) salience of self-efficacy and collective effectiveness; (2) perspective of the other; (3) salience of anti-discrimination norms and policies; (4) human rights prominence, justice social and equality; (5) compensation for reporting misbehaviour with heroic status (civil heroism); and (6) control condition (the baseline condition for comparison).

The data will be collected through an online anonymous questionnaire, disseminated in social networks and other available digital media (that will be identified later). A minimum of 220 participants is expected to respond to it. In the same way as other studies, participants will sign an informed consent form before answering the survey.

Study 5. Decrease in (actual) bystander behaviour towards online hate speech

This study (laboratory experiment) aims to test the effect of internal (moral self-regulation) and external (experimenter-induced control) social control mechanisms on decreasing bystander effect facing online hate speech.

During this study, participants will be allocated to a condition of pro-social behaviour (vs. control) found in the previous experiment to be effective in decreasing bystander effect, and a condition of social control (effective vs. control). In order to manipulate the effective social control condition, participants will read a text that will inform them how to proceed in case of detection of bad online behaviour, how many hateful contents were reported and how many cases denounced were treated effectively, that is, eliminated from social networks (effectiveness of mechanisms); in the control condition, participants will read a neutral text. Then, and orthogonally, half of the participants will be primed with a pro-social stimulus shown to be effective in the previous experiment, and participate in a fictitious team game supposedly with three other players in which one of them is supposedly an immigrant that will be the target of hate speech during the team interaction by another fictitious player. They will have the opportunity to interact with the other (fictitious) players (in fact, all the interaction – including hate speech – will be constructed by us). We will measure participants' actual behaviour in the team interaction after the "hate speech moment" and measure if they will report hate speech, support the victim, encourage the victim to report, support to the offender (adherence to hate speech), confront the offender, counteract the perpetrator's offence, or simply engage in bystander behaviour. After the interaction (fictitious game), they will respond to a small questionnaire able to measure the influence of other determinants measured in the decision they made in the experiment.

In this study, a minimum of 160 participants is expected. Data will be collected at the Social Psychology Laboratory of the FPCEUP. As in previous studies, the study will only

take place after reading an informed consent form. After participating in the study, a debriefing will be carried out and the experimental procedure will be clarified to each participant.

The RAW data in this project will include: database with name, surname, and email (for scheduling the focus group session), answers to questionnaires, session video files. The database will have an Excel format. The answers to the questionnaires will be processed to excel files, eliminating any sensitive and personal data (anonymization/codification). The session video files will be transcribed to word documents and anonymized/coded. All data RAW will not be preserved nor shared, because of the possibility of existing personal and sensitive data. They will be destroyed after they are processed. All types of data RAW will be stored until they are processed on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto and can be accessed only by the following members of the project: Isabel Pinto, Susana Salgado, and Catarina Carvalho.

Transcripts: session video files will be transcribed to word documents and will be destroyed after the transcription process. Transcriptions will not be shared, will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto and will be accessible only by Isabel Pinto, Susana Salgado, and Catarina Carvalho.

Processed data: excel and spss files processed from data collected through questionnaires; word files processed from transcripts. These data (without any personal and sensitive data) will be preserved on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto for 5 years after the project finalization and shared on an adequate data repository with a DOI assignment (that will be chosen later) without any restrictions. Their description standard will be Dublin Core and DDI.

In all studies (except study 2) the data will be collected through an online anonymous questionnaire with the Qualtrics software tool for the online questionnaire.

Other additional documents (such as Project Proposal, pilot studies, material construction, Informed consents, electronic messages, Ethics Committee agreement, requested reports for the funder, copies of Post-doc contract process, hiring of the communication team process, relevant emails exchange with “La Caixa” Foundation, etc.) might be created during the project and will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto, with access only by specific members of the team. More detailed information about these documents and their management will be added on the following versions of the DMP.

Responsibilities

Supervisors of the project: Isabel Rocha Pinto

Research team: Susana Salgado, José M. Marques, Catarina Carvalho, Sara Alves e Márcia Bernardo

Responsible entity: Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences of the University of Porto (FPCEUP)

Responsible for the collection: Isabel R. Pinto, Catarina Carvalho

for data analysis: Susana Salgado

for processing data: Isabel R. Pinto and Catarina Carvalho

for preservation data: Isabel R. Pinto, Catarina Carvalho

Session moderator and assistant researcher (Study 2): Isabel R. Pinto and Catarina Carvalho, respectively.

Others Researchers of the Project with access to the data RAW, to video transcripts, and to the processed data: Isabel R. Pinto, Catarina Carvalho, Sara Alves and Márcia Bernardo

Responsible for publishing and sharing data: Isabel Pinto and Catarina Carvalho

Responsible for DMP creation, update and monitoring: Yulia Karimova (ylaleo@gmail.com); Mafalda Lopes (mafalda@fpce.up.pt); Isabel Rocha Pinto (ipinto@fpce.up.pt).

All partners and members of the project need to agree with the created DMP and the rules defined therein. The DMP will be created according to the recommendations of the “La Caixa Foundation”, which in turn, follows RDM and GDPR requirements, such as open-science and FAIR principles.

FAIR data

1. Findability

To ensure that the data is findable it will be described according to the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) (<https://ddialliance.org/>) that is an international standard aimed at describing data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioural, economic, and health sciences, and the Dublin Core (DC) that is a metadata standard aimed at describing digital objects (<http://dublincore.org/>).

The processed data will be deposited on the data repository that allows the DOI assignment (it will be defined later). Each published dataset of the project will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) assigned by the chosen research data repository to make datasets more findable, accessible and reusable by others.

Information related to version control will also be added later on the next version .

2. Accessibility

The RAW data will only be accessible to Isabel Pinto, Catarina Carvalho, Susana Salgado and destroyed as soon as possible after transcripts or processing. The RAW data will be stored on the Laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto.

The transcripts will be accessible to Isabel Pinto, Catarina Carvalho, Susana Salgado, and destroyed after their processing. They will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto.

The processed data will be open without any restrictions on the data repository (that will be defined later) with DOI assignment, but only after publishing the respective papers. Moreover, they will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabel Pinto for 5 years after the conclusion of the project. Moreover, processed data from all the studies (and without any sensitive and personal information) will be made available to all researchers who wish to learn about the methodology used and/or replicate these studies in another population, through an Open Science platform (e.g. Open Science Framework; www.osf.io); this will be

defined with more detail, in a later DMP version.

Questionnaires' responses will be stored as Excel files for statistical processing (processed and anonymized). Only the members of the research team will have access to these files.

All collected data will be stored and retained only for the necessary period to fulfill the purposes for which they were collected and processed, namely scientific research and publishing.

The processed data (datasets) of the study may be published in scientific journals and academic newspapers, presented in seminars, conferences, classes or other activities with academic purposes, in which the results will only be mentioned in aggregate form and never individually, without any personal and sensitive information. Moreover, in case the datasets are requested by the scientific journal for publication, they will be shared for free, without any information that can identify participants.

3. Interoperability

To ensure the interoperability of the metadata, we will use the DCMI schema (<https://www.dublincore.org/schemas/>) and the DDI Schema (<https://ddialliance.org/Specification/>).

To ensure the interoperability of the data the preferred file formats for sharing will be *.xls/.xlsx, *.doc/.docx and *.sav (spss).

4. Reusability

The processed shared data can be reusable without any restrictions (but only after the publishing of the papers related to the data) and any limit of time. They will be publicly available at the data repository (to be defined later) with license Share-Alike, which allows to (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>):

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format;

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Data security

1. Data recovery processing, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The data collected through questionnaires will be stored on the servers of the company Qualtrics (<https://www.qualtrics.com/pt-br/>), until the end of the data collection

period. The Qualtrics software is fully compliant with the latest requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (<https://www.qualtrics.com/gdpr/>). The backups will be done by the Qualtrics company. These data will be long-term preserved. Other data will be stored on the laboratory PC of Isabe Pinto, with periodically back up in an external disk. Only Isabel Pinto will have access to the disk. Moreover, the RAW data, transcripts and their backups will be destroyed as soon as possible.

2. Coverage of the ethics review procedure context

Prior to being conducted, all studies will be submitted to our faculty research ethics committee describing the following ethics concerns:

1) All participants will be volunteers who agree to an informed consent form (and rules of the participation, and creation of the pseudonym). Data privacy policies and participants' anonymity will be respected, and data reports will ensure full confidentiality.

2) Social discrimination is a sensitive issue that may generate personal discomfort. Non-offensive, indirect, and (when possible) non-obtrusive means will be used in order to assess attitudes regarding targets of hate crime. The use of experimental plots ensuring experimental, psychological, and mundane realism in social psychological studies is a well-established research strategy, as is the use of post-experimental questionnaires and final debriefings as a means to deal with any possible psychological consequences of participation in such studies. The debriefing may be an opportunity for intervention, therefore, its planning and implementation will aim to raise participants' awareness of discrimination practices in order to prevent the incidence of such practices in their future.

Other matters

Participation in this study involves answering questions on hate crime against immigrants and in particular, about online hate speech. Participants will also be asked for some personal data such as age, gender and nationality. They will also be asked about their education level, employment condition, and political orientation. These data, as mentioned before, will be treated as aggregate and not individually, not allowing the identification of any participant. Only participants of Study 2 will be asked for their name and email address in order to schedule their participation in the study, and to fully explain the conditions for their participation. Aside from this procedure, participants' anonymity will be guaranteed. Regarding the other studies, participants' anonymity will be guaranteed since the beginning of the study.

The DMP will be monitored at least every 6 months. Monitorization will focus on registering the needed changes in all aspects related to the research data management issues. Moreover, it can also clarify the aspects related to the publication of the datasets on which data repository and their detailed description.

The project website (currently under construction) will be one of the tools to disseminate and communicate results of the studies, addressing targets such as common citizens and the community at large. More information will be added later.

This DMP will be published on the Platform of La Caixa Foundation, on Zenodo with DOI assignment and will be citable.

IPR ownership of data produced during the project is from the project team, however, in all communications that refer to project results should mention the collaboration between

the team and "la Caixa" Foundation and FCT, I.P. "la Caixa" Foundation has the right to publish and disseminate the results generated under the Project with the authors' acknowledgement.

Regarding dissemination on social networks, the team and "la Caixa" Foundation will agree on how the websites or logos of "la Caixa" Foundation and FCT, I.P. will be mentioned and linked. Scientific publications must include: "The project leading to these results has received funding from "la Caixa" Foundation and FCT, I.P. under the project code SR20-00136".

Complementary information

During the project in accordance with the data collection, their processing and analysis the need to create the Data Protection Impact Assessment and collaboration with the Data Protection Officer may emerge. More detailed information about this aspect will be added later in the following versions of the DMP.

The expected data size for preservation will be defined later.